

A Study on Etiological Pathophysiology and Management of Epilepsy

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ABSTRACT

Hippocrates was the among the earliest who discovered epilepsy and suggest that is hereditary rather than contagious. Epilepsy is a disorder of the brain characterized by repeated seizures. It is usually defined as a sudden alteration of behaviour due to a temporary change in the electrical functioning of the brain. Epilepsy, a disorder of unprovoked seizures is a multifaceted disease affecting individuals of all ages with a particular predilection for the very young and old. In addition to seizures, many patients often report cognitive and psychiatric problems associated with both the seizures themselves and its therapy. Epilepsy has numerous etiologies both idiopathic and acquired with a wide range of therapeutic responses. Despite numerous neuromodulatory devices, a large treatments available to control repetitive seizures including medications, diets, immunotherapy, surgery, and percentage of patients continue to suffer the consequences of uncontrolled seizures, which include psychosocial stigma and death.

KEYWORDS: Hippocrates, Epilepsy, seizures, immunotherapy, surgery etc.

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INTRODUCTION

There are millions of brain nerve cells in our cerebral cortex, and under normal circumstances, each cell carries a very small current. The electric waves transmit neural information and make us produce thoughts, feelings and activities, and coordinate functions such as breathing or heartbeat. Epilepsy is a problem with brain function (electric waves), which causes paroxysmal transient brain dysfunction (seizures). In addition to epilepsy, patients have a higher chance of having other problems (such as intellectual disability, cognitive problems, and emotional problems). Different parts of the brain are responsible for different functions. Depends on the location of seizure onset and propagation, patients with epilepsy can have different symptoms and different manifestations of seizures. Epilepsy is usually diagnosed

when someone has had more than one seizure. Seizures can affect your feelings, awareness or movement. Different types of seizures involve different things. These may include confusion, strange feelings, repetitive movements, 'blank' moments (where you are briefly unresponsive), muscle jerks, sudden falls, or jerking movements (while unconscious). The human cerebral cortex consists of 3 to 6 layers of neurons. The phylogenetically oldest part of the cortex (archipallium) has 3 distinct neuronal layers, and is exemplified by the hippocampus, which is found in the medial temporal lobe. The majority of the cortex (neocortex or neopallium) has 6 distinct cell layers and covers most of the surface of the cerebral hemispheres. A particularly important cortical structure in the pathophysiology of one of the more common epilepsy syndromes is the hippocampus.

TYPES

Fig: classification of epilepsy

EPIDEMIOLOGY

In a systematic review and meta-analysis of incidence studies, the pooled incidence rate of epilepsy was 61.4 per 100,000 person-years (95% CI 50.7–74.4) [1]. The incidence was higher in low/middle-income countries (LMIC) than in high-income countries (HIC), 139.0 (95% CI 69.4–278.2) vs. 48.9 (95% CI 39.0–61.1). This can be explained by the different structure of populations at risk and a greater exposure to perinatal risk factors, higher rates of CNS infections, and TBI in LMIC. The incidence of epilepsy is also higher in the lowest socioeconomic classes in HIC and, within the same population, people of differing ethnic origin [2]. Differences can be also explained by methodological issues, such as more stringent case verification and the exclusion of isolated and acute symptomatic seizures in some studies.

ETIOLOGY

1.IDIOPATHIC EPILEPSY: benign famililal neonatal convulsions ,autosomal dominant nocturnal frontal lobe epilepsy [3][6]

2. SYMPTOMATIC EPILEPSY:

PREDOMINANTLY GENETIC OR DEVELOPMENTAL CAUSATION :west syndrome;Lennox-Gastuat syndrome, neuronal ceroid lipofuscinosis ,mitochondrial cytopathy
PREDOMINANTLY AQUIRED CAUSATION:

hippocampal sclerosis , cerebral palsy, open head injury, closed head injury [4]

PROVOKED EPILEPSY: ,menstrual cycle and catamenial epilepsy ;sleep-wake cycle ;alcohol and toxin induced seizures [5]

3. COMMON SEIZURES CAUSED BY

- Birth trauma
- Congenital problems
- Fever/infection
- Metabolic and chemical imbalances in the body
- Genetic factors
- Brain tumor
- Neurological problems
- Drug withdrawal
- Medications
- Use of illicit drugs

RISK FACTORS

- Bleeding in the brain
- Serious brain injury or lack of confusion
- Blockage of arteries
- Alzheimers disease
- Illicit drug use
- Children with small age

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

Fig.2 A diagrammatic representation on pathophysiology of the epilepsy

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS

SYMPTOMS BASED ON THE TYPE OF SEIZURES:

1. **SIMPLE PARTIAL SEIZURES** : unusual smell or taste
 - Tingling in the arms and legs
 - Stiffness or twitching in part of your body
2. **COMPLEX PARTIAL SEIZURES**: making random noises
 - Rubbing your hands
 - Moving your arms around
3. **TONIC CLONIC SEIZURES**: loss of consciousness
 - Falling to the floor
 - Tongue biting
 - Difficulty in breathing
4. **ABSENCE SEIZURES** :stay blankly into space
Fluttering eyes, day dreaming
5. **MYOCLONIC SEIZURES** : electric shock
Sudden twitches or jerks

DIAGNOSIS

DIFFERENT TESTS TO DETECT EPILEPSY:

1. **EEG [ELECTROENCEPHALOGRAPH]**:In this test small sensors are attached to scalp which checks the unusual activity in which we seen in people with epilepsy
2. **BRAIN SCAN**:
MRI[MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING]:in this it uses the magnetic field which checks for the tumor in the brain ,and also the brain damage caused by the stroke or any scars present in the brain
3. **PET SCAN [POSITRON EMISSION TOMOGRAPHY]**:It is a nuclear medicine procedure which detects changes in the brain metabolism .

4. **SPECT SCAN[SINGLE PHOTON EMISSION COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY]**:It is also called" ICTAL SPECT" which detects or check changes in the blood flow, transmission between the cells

5. **INTRACRANIAL MONITORING**: To detect the characteristics of patients seizures physicians use this technology and correlate these finding with EEG .This test include

Depth electrodes: These are small, multi-contact probes that are inserted through small holes made in the skull and the coverings of the brain.

Strip and grid electrodes: These small platinum disks are set in a sheet of plastic and inserted underneath the covering of the brain called the dura.

Depth, strip and grid electrodes record brain wave activity in between and during seizures for planning epilepsy surgery.

6. **WADA TESTS**: helps determine the type of surgery that will best treat seizures while preserving areas of the brain associated with speech, memory and thinking functions.

PREVENTIONS OF EPILEPSY

- 1.By improving the maternal health[7]
- 2.Avoiding early teenage pregnancies which prevent epilepsy
- 3.By taking immunizations
- 4.Mandatory use of helmet for sports and traffic
- 5.Banning sports who have a increased risk of traumatic encephalopathies[8]

A Study on Etiological Pathophysiology and Management of Epilepsy

MANAGEMENT OF EPILEPSY

NON PHARMACOLOGICAL TREATMENT: patients choose for alternative therapies because they may be dissatisfied with antiepileptic drugs due to unpleasant side effects, long duration of seizures, failure to control seizures. the non pharmacological therapy includes

1. ketogenic diet: The diet induces ketosis which helps in the control of seizures [9]

MOA: The hormone called leptin which is generated by taking ketogenic diet, which helps in controlling seizures.

2. ALTERNATIVE /COMPLEMENTARY THERAPIES :

YOGA: Which relaxes body and mind, reduces stress, and helps in the control of seizures

AYURVEDA: the Ayurveda used to treat epilepsy by unblocking the channels of the heart and mind that may be clogged by excess of doshas and tumors. [11]

ASANAS OR POSTURES: Which help in maintaining the control of metabolic systems and the body functions, which calms nervous systems by increasing the stamina. [10]

3. ELECTROENCEPHALOGRAPHY

4. TRANSCRANIAL MAGNETIC STIMULATION

5. HERBAL MEDICINE

PHARMACOLOGICAL TREATMENT OF EPILEPSY: [12][13][14][15]

DRUG	BRAND NAME	INITIAL/STARTING DOSE	MAXIMUM DOSE	COMMENTS TARGET SERUM CONCENTRATION RANGE
BARBITURATES Phenobarbitone	Various	1-3mg/kg/day (10-20mg/kg LD)	180-300 mg	10-40 mcg/mL (43-172 µmol/L)
Primidone	Mysoline	100-125mg/kg	750-2,000 mg	5-10 mcg/mL (23-46 µmol/L)
BENZODIAZEPINES Clobazam	Onfi	≤30 kg 5 mg/day; >30 kg 10 mg/day	≤30 kg up to 20 mg; >30 kg up to 40 mg	0.03-0.3 ng/mL (0.1-1.0 nmol/L)
Clonazepam	Klonopin	1.5mg/kg	20mg	20-70 ng/mL (0.06-0.22 µmol/L)
Diazepam	Valium	PO: 4-40 mg IV: 5-10 mg	PO: 4-40 mg IV: 5-30 mg	100-1,000 ng/mL (0.4-3.5 µmol/L)
Lorazepam	Ativan	PO: 2-6 mg IV: 0.05 mg/kg IM: 0.05 mg/kg	PO: 10 mg IV: 0.05 mg/kg	10-30 ng/mL (31-93 nmol/L)
HYDANTOIN Phenytoin	Dilantin	PO: 3-5 mg/kg (200-400 mg) (15-20 mg/kg LD)	PO: 500-600 mg	Total: 10-20 mcg/mL (40-79 µmol/L) Unbound: 0.5-3 mcg/mL (2-12 µmol/L)
SUCCINAMIDE Ethosuximide	Zarotin	500mg/day	500-2,000 mg	40-100 mcg/mL (282-708 µmol/L)
OTHER Carbamazepine	Tegretol	400mg/day	400-2,400 mg	4-12 mcg/mL (17-51 µmol/L)
Ezogabine	Potiga	300mg/day	1200mg	Not defined
Felbamate	Felbatol	1200mg/day	3600mg	30-60 mcg/mL (126-252 µmol/L)
Gabapentin	Neurotin	300-900mg/day	4800mg	2-20 mcg/mL (12-117 µmol/L)
Locasamide	Vimpat	100mg/day	400mg	Not defined
Lamotrigine	Lamictal	25 mg every other day if on VPA; 25-50 mg/day if not on VPA	100-150 mg if on VPA; 300-500 mg if not on VPA	4-20 mcg/mL (16-78 µmol/L)
Levetiracetam	Keppra Keppra xr	500-1000mg/day	3000-4000mg	12-46 mcg/mL (70-270 µmol/L)

A Study on Etiological Pathophysiology and Management of Epilepsy

Oxcarbazepine	Trileptal	300-600mg/day	2400-3000mg	3–35 mcg/mL (MHD) (12–139 µmol/L)
Pregabalin	Lyrica	150mg/day	600mg	Not defined
Rufinamide	Banzel	400-800mg/day	3200mg	Not defined
Tiagabine	Gabitril	4-8mg/day	80mg	0.02–0.2 mcg/mL (0.05–0.5 µmol/L)
Topiramate	Topamax	25-50mg/day	200-1000mg	5–20 mcg/mL (15–59 µmol/L)
Valproic acid	Depakene Depakene SR Depakote Depakote ER Depacon	15mg/kg(500-1000mg)	60 mg/kg (3,000–5,000 mg)	50–100 mcg/mL (347–693 µmol/L)
Vigabatrin	Sabril	100mg/day	3000m	0.8–36 mcg/mL (6–279 µmol/L)
Zonisamide	zonegran	100-200mg/day	600mg	0.8–36 mcg/mL (6–279 µmol/L)

NEW DRUG FOR EPILEPSY

The U.S Food and Drug Administration today approved XCOPRI(cenobamate tablet) to treat partial –onset seizures in adults .cenobamate is under the class of medications called anticonvulsants .it works by decreasing abnormal electrical activity in the brain .[16]

NEW TECHNOLOGY TO TREAT EPILEPSY

The machine called ROSA allows surgeons to more precisely target parts of the brain responsible for epileptic seizures[17].

BEST VITAMIN TO TREAT EPILEPSY

Vitamin D may help to control seizures

Some anti-seizure medications interfere with how vitamin D is processed in the body .supplemental vitamin D may be necessary for people who have these risk factors to maintain normal blood levels.

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A Study on Etiological Pathophysiology and Management of Epilepsy

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